
A Historical Examination of Socio-Cultural and Economic Interconnections Among Ethnic Groups in Manipur

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ABSTRACT

Manipur is home to various ethnic groups, including the Meiteis, Nagas, and Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribes, each with distinct socio-political aspirations. The Meiteis seek to retain territorial integrity, the Nagas demand the integration of Naga-inhabited areas, and the Kuki-Chin-Mizo groups seek a separate administration. These differing aspirations at times cause strain in the inter-community relationship. This article explores their socio-cultural and economic ties from a historical perspective using qualitative analysis of significant events and secondary data. It examines their common gods, matrimonial alliances, folklore, cultural exchanges, and festivals. Based on these investigations, the study argues that a shared origin, common heritage, cultural interchange, a complex network of interconnectedness, mutual respect, and harmonious cohabitation were the essence of the socio-cultural and economic relationship among them. Accepting this shared heritage is crucial for advancing unity and interdependence among Manipur's communities. Understanding these differences can foster progress and inclusivity in this culturally diverse region

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Situated as India's portal to Southeast Asia, the geographical and environmental characteristics of Manipur have significantly influenced the evolution of its historical trajectory and cultural fabric. It is a

state in the North Eastern Region of India, surrounded by hills. The state extends from 92°58'23.422" East to 94°43'35.553" East longitudes and 23°49'45.530" North to 25°42'1.456" North latitudes. The state is 22,327 km² in size. It shares a 352 km international border with Myanmar in the southeastern region. It borders the Indian state of Nagaland to the North, Assam to the west, and Mizoram to the south. According to the 2011 Population census, the state's population is 2,855,794. From a geographical perspective, the state can be divided into two distinct regions – the valley (plain) and the hills. The States's hills cover 90% of this geographical area, leaving a small valley of 2,238 sq. km, constituting just 10% of the state's total land area. The state's total population density is 128 people per sq. km. The population density in Manipur varies significantly across its geographical regions. There are 730 people per sq. km in the valley, while in the hills, it is much lower at 61 per sq. km (Directorate of Economic & Statistics Government of Manipur Lamphelpat, 2021).

The present name Manipur literally means 'land of gems.' The state has had different names at various times in history and was known by various names to its neighbours. Referring to an early Meitei text titled "*Sanamahi Laikan*," Kamei (2007) **asserts** that King Garibniwaz introduced the name 'Manipur' during the early eighteenth century. Before this, it was known as '*Kangleipak*,' '*Poireipak*,' and '*Meitrabak*' among its people. The Burmese referred to the state and its people as '*Kathe*.' The Shans, who resided in the region east of the Ningthzee or Khyendwen River, referred to Manipur as '*Cassay*,' and the Burmese word '*Kathe*' is a corruption of the term. The people of Cachar called it '*Moglie*' (Pemberton, 1835). '*Meklee*' was the Assamese term for Manipur and its people (Kabui, 2007). Manipur's recorded history spans millennia, revealing an advanced political organization, a stable cultural network, and a well-developed literary language. The region engaged in trade and commerce with Southeast Asian countries, facilitated by gold and silver currency. Manipur had victorious military campaigns against neighbouring nations and occasional defeats like any ancient civilization. Despite the defeat in the Anglo-Manipuri War of 1891, Manipur was not annexed to the British Empire and she was allowed to continue with her native rule. Following the departure of the British, a constitutional monarchy was established in Manipur under the provisions of the Manipur Constitution Act of 1947. However, on October 15, 1949, Manipur merged with the Dominion of India, marking a significant transition in its history (Sanajaoba, 1988).

The Meiteis, the largest ethnic group, mainly populate the valley region. It also has several tribal localities and a substantial Muslim community called the Meitei Pangal. The hills, on the other hand, are

home to many tribes. The people in the hills are broadly divided into two major groups of tribes; the Naga and the Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribes. Historically, the three principal communities coexisted harmoniously engaging in close interactions that shaped their cultures and lifestyles. This deep connection is reflected in the famous adage, ‘*Chingburoi Tamburoi*,’ symbolizing a bond rooted in love, friendship, trust, and mutual respect. However, in recent years, growing socio-political differences have strained these relationships, leading to tensions among the communities. Against this backdrop, the present study examines the historical socio-cultural and economic ties that once defined their coexistence, offering insights into their involving dynamics.

Importance of the Study

Shared socio-cultural and economic ties—such as common deities, matrimonial alliances, festivals, linguistic affinities, and economic interactions—have long shaped inter-community relationships. Analysing these historical connections provides deeper insights into patterns of cooperation, interdependence, and cultural exchange. Identifying these commonalities can inform inclusive policymaking, fostering inter-community collaboration, equitable resource distribution, and social integration. Furthermore, such research facilitates meaningful dialogue by uncovering shared histories, reinforcing cultural connections, and fostering mutual understanding. These efforts, in turn, help strengthen communal harmony and encourage peaceful coexistence.

Shared Cultural and Social Bonds

Common Gods and Goddesses

The Meiteis and the tribes of the state have a number of common gods and goddesses. The Meiteis in the valley have gods and goddesses whose abodes are in the hills, such as *Lainingthou Nongshaba* at Mende hills; Lord *Thangjing* at Koubru hills who later came to the present abode at Moirang; etc. Several other deities have places of worship not only in the valley but also in the hills, like *Pureilomba*, *Koubru*, *Chingkhei Ningthou*, and so on. The Kom tribe of Kakching Mantak village, Manipur, worships the Meitei god *Lainingthou Nongshaba*. The Meiteis and Koireng tribe worship the same god – *Lainingthou Koubru*. Lord *Pakhangba* and *Haipou Ragawang* of the Kabuis have similar coronation stories, while *Lainingthou Sanamahi* is revered by various tribes, including the Kabuis, Chothes, Kuki, Tangkhul, and Purum (Haobijam, 2013). The Anal tribes residing in the Chandel district

of Manipur hold *Ibudhou Wangpuren* (also known as ***Wangbren***) in high reverence. The origins of this worship trace back to a significant event: the marriage between Lord *Wangbren* and an Anal maiden. Remarkably, even today the Anal community visits the holy shrine of *Wangbren* to pay their reverence to the deity (Naorem, 2020). The shared worship of gods and goddesses among various ethnic groups in Manipur signifies cultural exchange and underscores a common ancestral heritage and historical interconnectedness among the people of Manipur.

Matrimonial Alliances

There are also numerous accounts of matrimonial alliances between tribal communities and the Meitei people in their myths and legends. For instance, there is a story of *Pakhangba*, a revered deity of the Meiteis marrying *Khamlangtaobi*, the daughter of a *Khullakpa* (tribal chief) from Tamang Village. Similarly, the six Meitei maidens of Luwang, or *Luwang Chanus*, also known as *Khongjomnupis* married six bachelors from the Haoku tribe and resided atop the Koubru hills. *Chingshomba/Nongpok Ningthou* of the highlands in the east married *Wangamlon Apanbi/Panthoibee* of the Ningthouja clan from the valley and moved from the Khangkhui cave to the Shelloi Langmai hills. (Haobijam, 2013). The *Cheitharon Kumpapa* also records a maiden from Maram tribe, referred to as Maram Leima Pongu, entering into matrimony with the Meitei King in 1581 (Parratt, 2005). Intermarriage serves as a powerful indicator of social integration and cultural blending (Furtado, 2015). This matrimonial relationship between ethnic groups serves as a marker of cultural exchange and social integration. These accounts further signify the close relation between the people of the hills and the valley characterised by social cohesion and cultural convergence.

Another notable illustration of the close cultural affinity among several ethnic groups is evident between the Tangkhuls and Meiteis, reflected in numerous aspects of their traditional customs. For instance, one essential piece of clothing that a Meitei bride has to take along with her at the time of her marriage is the '*Luirumphi*,' a traditional Tangkhul shawl. It is customary for the bride to gift a *Luirumphi* to the groom, usually woven by the Meitei. In addition, the Meitei people are known for weaving a unique type of cloth called *Raivat Kachon*, which features intricate embroidery depicting various animals such as elephants, horses, dogs, and so on. This type of cloth is exclusively worn by the Nagas, who belong to noble families (Hugh, 2002). This vibrant cultural interconnection signifies the close socio-cultural affinity that the two communities have.

Folklores and Festivals

In addition to Matrimonial alliances, the Meitei and the hills tribes of Manipur exhibit a substantial degree of socio-cultural affinity. Numerous folklores of the major ethnic groups demonstrate their shared socio-cultural traits. Folklore is the body of expressive culture, including myths, legends, folk tales, proverbs, riddles, jokes, material culture, etc. Exploring the relationship between folklore and culture, Chungkham (2021) writes that anthropologists can construct a society through folklore. She further points out that anthropologists consider folklore as an aspect of culture, not the whole/entire thing. No community is without some folklore, no matter how primitive or contemporary. Any anthropological research that does not include folklore is deemed incomplete. Folklore holds significant cultural and social value, transmitting knowledge and collective memory from generation to generation, preserving memories, and connecting us to our roots. The scholarly reinterpretation of the folklore can further the conversation on sociopolitical problems and community relationships. It can offer insightful information for community development and policy-making projects that support social harmony and equitable growth in societies characterised by ethnic plurality. Considering the importance of folklore, one may explore the rich folklores of the different ethnic groups to examine the commonalities and shared ancestry that run through these fascinating stories, all proudly recounted by the people.

It is worth noting that, in the earlier periods of Manipur's history, the tribes such as the Naga and Kuki-Chin-Mizo group of tribes were not known by their current group nomenclatures. Instead, they were known by their individual tribal names, such as Tangkhul, Maring, Maram, Chiru, Kom, Khongjai, etc. In the subsequent sections of the paper, both specific tribal names and broader group nomenclatures are being used depending on the concerned context.

Folklores Signifying a Common Origin

The captivating folklore of the tribes provides fascinating insights into their origin. The Kom people's folklore narrates that their forefathers emerged from a hole (Kilong, 2002). Similarly, the Tarao believe their origin is from the *Tukleikhur* cave (Tarao, 2002). Likewise, the Purum ancestors are said to have sprung out of *Khurpui*, also known as "the great hole" (Purum, 2002). The Mates, Paites, Zous, Lushais, Koms, Thangals, and many others also share a similar tale of their ancestors coming out from

the Khul or cave (Mate, 2002). The shared elements within their folk traditions suggest a profound connection to their ancient heritage.

Folktale of Mao Maram

There is a folktale about three brothers in Mao Maram. It recounts the story of the brothers leaping over a canal. The eldest brother effortlessly cleared the canal, landing gracefully on a mound, and became the progenitor of the Kuki tribe, known not to use water often. The second brother, who barely missed the canal bank, became the progenitor of the Nagas who are understood to occasionally interact with water. The youngest could not jump over the canal and fell into the water, getting thoroughly soaked. He eventually became the Meiteis, known to frequent use water for bathing, laundry, and other daily activities. (Haobijam, 2013).

Folklore of Thangal tribe

According to a folktale of the Thangal tribe, the progenitors of the Thangals, Tangkhuls and Meiteis lived together once. However, in course of time, they parted ways and followed their own paths. The eldest went to the Thangal Surung (cave) and became the progenitor of the Thangals. The middle one went towards the east, settled at Hundung, and became the progenitor of the Tangkhuls. The youngest one went down into the valley, settled at Kangla, and became the progenitor of the Meiteis. Before their separation, the brothers agreed to stay in touch and maintain their bond by getting together often.

As a symbol of their bond, the elder brothers would bring the finest gifts of the first crops from the hills to their younger brother, who lived in the valley. There is also a strong belief that there is a subterranean connection between the Thangal Sarung and Kangla caves (Khangba, 2002) which further underlines the close relationship between the two. This folktale also symbolically represents the elder siblings' care and concern for their younger ones.

Khongjai Folklore

The Khongjai/Thadou legend tells the story of two brothers embroiled in a heated dispute over the rightful ownership of a piece of cloth. Their mother stepped in to calm down the brewing conflict and intervened and settle the dispute. The mother, who took the side of her younger son, cut the cloth into two parts. The younger son received the larger cloth and later became the Meitei, who still wears

plenty of cloth by covering the maximum parts of the body. Conversely, the elder son received the lesser portion. As a result, he was scantily clad. He went on to become the ancestor of the Khongjai/Thadou (Haobijam, 2013). Such a legend emphasises close filial ties between the Meiteis and the Khongjais/Thadous.

Folktales of this nature possess considerable socio-cultural significance, offering valuable insights into the shared ancestry of both hill and plain communities. Such folktales may be retold and reinterpreted in a way that encourages harmony and respect amongst various ethnic groups. This will contribute to fostering peaceful cohabitation and enhancing inter-community relationships.

Mera Haojongba: A festival of Unity

Mera Haojongba is an annual gathering of people from the hills and plain, celebrating their close relationship. The festival serves as a reminder of the love and friendship shared between the two groups (Senjam, 1996). It is celebrated to commemorate the solidarity among different ethnic groups. The festival is celebrated on the fifteenth lunar day of the Mera month which may fall either in September or October. Combat dances, feasts of strength, along with sporting events and cultural performances, and a feast at the end mark the festival. It is attended by the king of Manipur, village chiefs and residents of the nearby hills. A significant aspect of the festival is the exchange of gifts between the king and the village chiefs. A large feast marks the end of the event. The king even provided *Mithun* meals to those coming from the hills. This led to the famous Manipuri phrase ‘*Mera Sanduba*. *Mera* is the month when the festival takes place and ‘*Sanduba*’ implies death of many *mithuns*. It is one of the most significant festivals in Manipur that promotes and strengthens friendly and harmonious relationships among the people of the state (Kamei, 2014).

Itao Shannaba or Ngai Shannaba

Another special relationship shared between the people from the hills and valley is evidenced by the tradition of what is known as ‘*Itao shannaba*’ or ‘*Ngai shannaba*’ (*Itao* or *Ngai* signifies a friend in its purest form and *shannaba* implies to mutually agree) (Haobijam, 2013). It signifies the bonding of a special friendship. This bonding transcends geographical and ethnic barriers. *Itao* signifies floating or sailing together in the same blood. Consequently, such friends are considered friends by blood, which is understood to be of the noblest of all forms of friendships. Instances of pledges to become friends by blood between the people of hills and the Meiteis are documented in the

Cheitharon Kumpapa. As reported in *Cheitharon Khmpapa* “9 Sunday, most of the Haos from the eastern area were made to pledge to become blood brothers with most of the Meitei men in high positions.” (Parratt, 2005. p – 112). In another instance, the *Cheitharon Kumpapa* records an event where all the nobles, including the King, pledged to become blood brothers with the Lairam Tangkhuns.

Many of the present generation still remember their grandparents fondly recalling and sharing to them the friendship they shared with the *Itaos* or *Ngais* from the hills with much love, affection and tenderness. Such a heartwarming relationship was a hallmark of the bond shared between the people of the hills and valley, underscoring a strong sense friendship and fraternity.

Shared Linguistic Heritage

Most people in the region belong to Mogoloid stock and predominantly speak Tibeto-Burman languages. Emphasising the intimate linguistic connections, Kamei (2017) agrees with Grierson’s assertion that the Meitei share ancestral ties with Tibeto-Burman speakers from southwestern China, eastern Tibet, and upper Burma. This historical connection elucidates their affinity with other Tibeto-Burman tribes, such as the Nagas and Kukis, which are considered less advanced.

Additionally, the Meitei language, Meeteilon, the mother tongue of the Meitei people, is the lingua-franca of the state. It is widely acknowledged that numerous tribes within the Naga and Kuki-Chin-Mizo communities exhibit linguistic multiplicity, and their inter-tribal communication, especially among the Naga tribes is primarily conducted in the Manipuri language.

While examining the socio-cultural relationship between the hills and plain of Manipur, Senjam (1996) asserts the significance of two common sayings, ‘*Chingburoi Tamburoi*,’ and ‘*Haoringjel Nairingjel*’. According to him these two sayings throw significant insights to the nature of relationship the two shared between them in the past. The first saying, ‘*Chingburoi tamburoi*’ conveys sentiments of love, affection, mutual understanding, and friendship that they shared. Conversely, the second saying, ‘*Haoringjel Nairingjel*,’ indicates elements of mutual distrust, animosity, and antagonism that existed in the relationship between the two. However, S. Mangi further contends that the relationship was primarily the one symbolised by ‘*Chingburoi-Tamburoi*’ which signifies an organic bond of love, friendship, trust and mutual respect. Such expression underscored the enduring traditional relationship that has existed between the two groups since their earliest interactions. Gangte (2013) also opines that

the Meiteis, Nagas, and Kukis, despite their distinct identities, can be traced back to a shared origin. For her, this shared origin is further evidenced by their historical cohabitation within the same territory, the evolution of their political structures, and their mutual exchange of societal advancements. She believes that their way forward has to be not one of isolation from one another but of collective progression and unity

Trade and Economic Relations

In ancient times, the economic relationship between the hills and the valley was in the form of an exchange of goods between them. At the time, this practice was known as '*pot khanba*' by some Meitei villages. Such a tradition signifying the economic relationship between the two is also further manifested in the emergence of a market in Imphal operated exclusively by hills people known as '*Hao Keithel. Hao*' is the term used by the Meiteis to denote the tribal people. '*Keithel*,' on the other hand, is derived from two Manipur terms, '*Kei*' and '*Thei*' or '*Theiba*'. '*Kei*' means storehouse, and '*Thei*' means showing or laying out the produces or objects for trade through a barter system or money circulation. Hence the name '*Hao Keithel*' (Okram, 2021). A similar relationship the Meiteis had with the Maram tribe is evidenced by the story of one *Makimei Salikijang* or Meitei Bazar Shed which was there once in Maram Khullen. It served as a platform for the exchanging goods between the two (Maram, 2002).

Another important economic interaction between hills and valley could be seen with salt as a barter item. Salt, an essential resource, was abundant in the valley and scarce in the hills. Numerous natural salt wells have been present near the foothills since historical times and remain so till day. This disparity facilitated a robust barter economy, driven by the hills' lack of salt and the valleys' abundance of it. The salt from these wells was used as barter items to be exchanged with tobacco, ginger, cloths and cotton from the surrounding tribes (Pemberton, 1835).

It is noteworthy that the current government in Manipur, headed by Chief Minister N. Biren, has proposed the construction of a new '***Hao Market***' with a view to accommodate vendors from different tribes of the state. He further emphasised that the proposed market will set a great example of unity and oneness in diversity ('Hao Market' of 32 tribes of Manipur to come up in Imphal, 2022). This Hao Keithel could be seen as a manifestation of the intricate economic interdependence of the hills and valley in Manipur.

Colonial Accounts on the Close Affinity Between Hills and Valley Communities

After examining the customs, dialects, and cultural ties between the Meitei and the neighbouring hills tribes, McCulloch (1980) postulated that the main Meitei tribes or clans are descended from the surrounding hills tribes. Specifically, these hills tribes include the Naga and the Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribes in present-day Manipur. Hodson (1908) highlights the parallels between the Meiteis, who inhabited the Manipur valley, and the hills tribes. He underscores their shared characteristics with regard to their internal societal organizations, habits, and manners. Furthermore, Hodson explains how the Meiteis transitioned from a relatively primitive culture to one of comparative civilization due to successive foreign invasions (including Shan Burmese, English, and Hindu influences). He contends that the Meitei's resemblance to the Nagas and Kukis of the hills is undeniable even after this change. In examination of the affinities between the Meitei and Naga tribes in Manipur, T.C. Hudson (1908) wrote: The annals of Manipur leave it impossible to doubt that an earlier period the intercourse between the Meitheis and the Naga tribes was coloured by considerable intimacy which may explain, if it does not altogether justify, the legend that at one time the Manipuris used to marry Naga girls from the great village Maram. In a passage in the narrative of the reign of the reformer Gharib Nawaz, we find mention of an invitation to the entire Naga chief. (p. 110)

Colonial accounts eloquently documented the intertwined heritage and profound cultural and social bonds connecting the hills and valley communities. Their accounts highlighted the economic interdependence, symbiotic relationships, harmonious coexistence, and linguistic similarities among the Meitei, Naga, and Kuki-Chin-Mizo peoples.

Conclusion

The diverse socio-cultural and economic relationships between the three main ethnic groups of Manipur – the Meiteis, the Nagas, and the Kuki-Chin-Mizos showcase an organic web of shared history and interdependence. The historical approach highlights a history of peaceful cohabitation that is characterized by close cultural intercourse and mutual respect. Folklore and festivals like the Mera Haojongba, emphasise enduring relationships and shared heritage. Matrimonial ties and common deities further show how closely these groups have come together. Economic interactions, particularly through markets like the '*Hao Keithel*,' *Makimei Salikijang* etc. demonstrate the longstanding economic reciprocity between the hills and valley inhabitants. The tradition of '*Itao shanaba*' or '*Ngai shanaba*' show how personal relationship among the people of the hills and the valley transcended geographical and ethnic barriers thereby contributing to the sense of solidarity among them. As Manipur navigates

contemporary challenges, understanding and preserving these traditional ties can provide a foundation for continued peace and inclusivity. This in turn will help in ensuring that the state's diverse cultural landscape remains a source of strength and cohesion. Embracing this essence of their past relations is also fundamental for creating a tapestry of unity, celebrating their rich cultural mosaic, and paving the way for a harmonious future. Such an approach would promote inter-community cohesion and also foster a sense of mutual respect and understanding. Further research is required to understand the contemporary dynamics of the inter-community relations among the people, and explore how traditional bonds might be leveraged to foster peace and inclusivity in this culturally rich region.

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